

**O‘ZBEKISTON DAVLAT JISMONIY TARBIYA VA SPORT ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR
INSTITUTI LABARATORIYASIDA YENGIL ATLETIKACHILARNING
ANTROPOMETRIK VA FUNKSIONAL KO‘RSATKICHLARI BO‘YICHA QAYD
ETILGAN NATIJALARINING ASOSIY STATISTIK XARAKTERISTIKALARI.**

Allamurodov Sh.I.

O‘zDJTSU., Professor.

Yarashev K.D.

O‘zDJTSU., Professor.

Xasanova N.R.

O‘zDJTSU., Katta o‘qituvchi.

Kazoqov R.T.

O‘zDJTSU., Katta o‘qituvchi.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14048472>

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada O‘zbekiston davlat jismoniy tarbiya va sport ilmiy tadqiqotlar instituti laboratoriyasida yengil atletikachilarning antropometrik va funksional ko‘rsatkichlari bo‘yicha qayd etilgan natijalarining asosiy statistik xarakteristikalari haqida fikr yuritilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: Harakat malakasi, bosh miya po‘stlog‘ida ko‘p sonli asab torlari, harakat ko‘nikmasi, jismoniy sifatlarning rivojlanish darajasi.

**THE MAIN STATISTICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE RESULTS RECORDED IN
THE LABORATORY OF THE UZBEKISTAN STATE INSTITUTE OF PHYSICAL
EDUCATION AND SPORTS SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH ON ANTHROPOMETRIC AND
FUNCTIONAL INDICATORS OF ATHLETICS.**

Abstract. This article discusses the main statistical characteristics of the results of the anthropometric and functional indicators of track and field athletes recorded in the laboratory of the State Institute of Physical Education and Sports Scientific Research of Uzbekistan.

Keywords: Movement skills, a large number of nerve fibers in the cortex of the brain, movement skills, the level of development of physical qualities.

**ОСНОВНЫЕ СТАТИСТИЧЕСКИЕ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКИ РЕЗУЛЬТАТОВ
ЗАФИКСИРОВАННЫ В ЛАБОРАТОРИИ УЗБЕКСКОГО ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОГО
ИНСТИТУТА ФИЗИЧЕСКОГО ВОСПИТАНИЯ И СПОРТА НАУЧНО-
ИССЛЕДОВАТЕЛЬСКИХ РАБОТ ПО АНТРОПОМЕТРИЧЕСКИМ И
ФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНЫМ ПОКАЗАТЕЛЯМ ЛЕГКОЙ АТЛЕТИКИ.**

Аннотация. В статье рассмотрены основные статистические характеристики результатов антропометрических и функциональных показателей легкоатлетов, зарегистрированных в лаборатории Государственного научно-исследовательского института физической культуры и спорта Узбекистана.

Ключевые слова: Двигательные навыки, большое количество нервных волокон в коре головного мозга, двигательные навыки, уровень развития физических качеств.

Dunyoda yengil atletikaning qisqa masofalarga yugurish turi ommalashgan sport turlaridan hisoblanadi. Sport natijalari kundan kunga o‘zib borishi qisqa masofalarga yuguruvchi

o‘smirlarni yillik tayyorgarlik mashg‘ulotlarini samarali taqsimlash uslubiyatini takomillashtirishni taqozo etmoqda. Qisqa masofaga yuguruvchilarni tayyorlash bo‘yicha dunyodagi yetakchi olimlar bilan bir qatorda yurtimizdagi mutaxassislar ham mashg‘ulot uslubiyatini takomillashtirish bo‘yicha izlanishlar olib borganlar. Mualliflar mashg‘ulotlarda texnikani to‘g‘ri o‘rgatish va vosita usullarni qo‘llanish uslubiyati e‘tibor qaratib kelgan lekin qisqa masofalarga yuguruvchi talabalarni yillik tayyorgarlik mashg‘ulotlarini taqsimlanish hajmi bo‘yicha juda kam ma‘lumotlar berilgan.

Shu boisdan hozirgi kunda bizning fikrimizcha qisqa masofaga yuguruvchi o‘smirlarimiz yaxshi sport natijasiga erisha olmaganligi mashg‘ulot jaraenini takomillashtirish zaruriyatiga e‘tibor qaratishni taqozo etadi.

Bugungi kunda qisqa masofalarga yuguruvchilarning yillik tayyorgarlik bosqichini taqsimlashning yangi texnologiyasini ishlab chiqish, qo‘llaniladigan vosita usullarni saralash, umumiy jismoniy tayyorgarlikining optimal nisbatlarini izlab topish, biomexanik parametrlarni aniqlash va tahlil qilishiga e‘tibor dolzarb ahamiyat kasb etadi. O‘zbekiston Davlat jismoniy tarbiya va sport universiteti talabalari yengil atletikachilarning texnik usullarni (tezkorlik va aniqlik) bajarishida ularning jismoniy tayyorgarligi bilan korrelyatsion bog‘liqligi, tajriba va nazorat guruhlarining dastlabki testlash bo‘yicha olingan ma‘lumotlari keltirilgan. O‘zbekiston Davlat jismoniy tarbiya va sport universiteti jismoniy tarbiya yengil atletika talabalarilarning jismoniy va texnik tayyorgarligi bo‘yicha tadqiqotdan oldin olingan natijalar bo‘yicha ma‘lumotlar keltirilgan. Keltirilgan ma‘lumotlar sohaning taniqli olimlari tomonidan asoslangan fikrlarni ta’kidlaydi va tanlangan mavzuni yanada boyitishga xizmat qiladi.

1-jadval.

O‘zbekiston davlat jismoniy tarbiya va sport ilmiy tadqiqotlar instituti laboratoriyasida nazorat (n=14) va tajriba (n=14) guruhlariga mansub talabalarning tajriba oxirida antropometrik va funksional ko‘rsatkichlari bo‘yicha qayd etilgan natijalarining asosiy statistik xarakteristikalari. («3D Motion Analyzer» apparatida).

No	Talaba-sportchilari ng tana qismlari	Tana qismlari xarakati	Chap tomon	O‘ng tomon	Diapazon	Diagramma	Tana tuzilish xolati
1	Inson tanasi	Egiluvchanlik	0 ⁰	107 ⁰	107 ⁰		
		Yonga egilish	-180 ⁰	14 ⁰	194 ⁰		
2	Bo‘yin	Egiluvchanlik	-8 ⁰	31 ⁰	39 ⁰		
		Yonga egilish	-13 ⁰	19 ⁰	32 ⁰		
		Aylanish	-4 ⁰	18 ⁰	22 ⁰		

3	Yelkalar	Egiluvchanlik	-69°	87°	156°		
		Burilishlar	0°	83°	83°		
4	Tirsaklar	Egiluvchanlik	28°	134°	162°		
5	Son	Egiluvchanlik	-14°	70°	84°		
		Burilishlar	5°	16°	21°		
6	Tizza	Egiluvchanlik	19°	110°	129°		
7	Boldir panja	Egiluvchanlik	-27°	0°	27		

2-jadval.

O'zbekiston davlat jismoniy tarbiya va sport ilmiy tadqiqotlar instituti laboratoriyasida nazorat (n=14) va tajriba (n=14) guruhlariga mansub talabalarning antropometrik va funksional ko'rsatkichlari bo'yicha qayd etilgan natijalarining asosiy statistik xarakteristikalari («3D Motion Analyzer» apparatida) bo'yicha talaba-sportchilarning tana qismlari va diapazon tuzilish xolati ko'rsatilgan.

Tajriba oxiri	Biomexanik Ko'rsatkich	Nazorat guruhi			Tajriba guruhi			t	P
		X _{o'rt}	σ	V, %	X _{o'rt}	σ	V, %		
1	Inson tanasi	0.21	0.008	3.8	0.12	0.009	7.5	2.3	<0.05
2	Bo'yin	41.2	3.5	8.5	44.2	4.1	9.2	3.6	<0.01
3	Yelkalar	88.2	4.5	5.1	91.2	5.2	5.7	3.1	<0.01
4	Tirsaklar	52.1	4.3	8.2	56.3	5.1	9.0	4.5	<0.001
5	Son	4.2	0.5	11.9	4.9	0.4	8.2	2.4	<0.05
6	Tizza	38.2	2.4	6.3	33.5	3.5	10.4	6.4	<0.001
7	Boldir panja	1.74	0.02	1.1	1.89	0.03	1.5	2.2	<0.05

3-jadval.

Nazorat (n=14) va tajriba (n=14) guruhlariga mansub talabalarning qisqa masofaga yugurishda biomexanik ko'rsatkichlarining qiyosiy tahlili.

Tajriba oxiri	Biomexanik Ko'rsatkich	Nazorat guruhi			Tajriba guruhi			t	P
		X _{o'rt}	σ	V, %	X _{o'rt}	σ	V, %		
1	Kuch chiqarish vaqti	0.21	0.008	3.8	0.12	0.009	7.5	2.3	<0.05
2	Start burchagi (Starting Angle)	41.2	3.5	8.5	44.2	4.1	9.2	3.6	<0.01
3	Tana va oyoqlar burchagi	88.2	4.5	5.1	91.2	5.2	5.7	3.1	<0.01
4	Tana og'irlik markazi balandligi	52.1	4.3	8.2	56.3	5.1	9.0	4.5	<0.001
5	Tezlanish (Acceleration)	4.2	0.5	11.9	4.9	0.4	8.2	2.4	<0.05
6	Maksimal tezlanish masofasi	38.2	2.4	6.3	33.5	3.5	10.4	6.4	<0.001
7	Qadam uzunligi	1.74	0.02	1.1	1.89	0.03	1.5	2.2	<0.05
8	Qadam chastotasi	3.66	0.4	10.9	5.3	0.5	9.4	5.7	<0.001
9	Qo'l harakat tezligi	2.1	0.2	9.5	2.8	0.3	10.7	3.3	<0.01

Nazorat (n=14) va tajriba (n=14) guruhlariga mansub talabalarning jismoniy tayyorgarlik testlari bo'yicha tajriba boshida 100 metr nasofaga yugurishda qayd etilgan natijalarining asosiy statistik xarakteristikalarini solishtirganimizda absaliyut foiz 0,33, nisbiy foiz 2,50. t student kriteriysi 0,51, $p > 0,5$ extimollik darajasini taskil qildi. 200 metr nasofaga yugurishda qayd etilgan natijalarining asosiy statistik xarakteristikalarini solishtirganimizda absaliyut foiz 0,37, nisbiy foiz 1,31. t student kriteriysi 0,25, $p > 0,5$ extimollik darajasini taskil qildi, 400 metr nasofaga yugurishda qayd etilgan natijalarining asosiy statistik xarakteristikalarini solishtirganimizda absaliyut foiz 0,02, nisbiy foiz 2,27. t student kriteriysi 0,40, $p > 0,6$ extimollik darajasini taskil qildi, 100 m ga yugurishda qadamlar soni qayd etilgan natijalarining asosiy statistik xarakteristikalarini solishtirganimizda absaliyut foiz 0,04, nisbiy foiz 1,74. t student kriteriysi 0,34, $p > 0,7$ extimollik darajasini taskil qildi, 100 m ga yugurishda qadamlar sur'ati, qad/s, da qayd etilgan natijalarining asosiy statistik xarakteristikalarini solishtirganimizda absaliyut foiz 0,93, nisbiy foiz 1,97. t student kriteriysi 0,41, $p > 0,6$ extimollik darajasini taskil qildi, 100 m ga yugurishda qadamlar uzunligi qayd etilgan natijalarining asosiy statistik xarakteristikalarini solishtirganimizda absaliyut foiz 0,06, nisbiy foiz 1,41. t student kriteriysi 0,25, $p > 0,8$ extimollik darajasini taskil qildi.

Xulosalar. Anketa so'rovnomasi natijalarining tahlili shuni ko'rsatdiki, maxsus jismoniy tayyorgarlik darajasini takomillashtirish muammosi bo'yicha mutaxassislarining fikrlari turlicha bo'ldi: so'ralgan mutaxassislarining 77,4% antropometrik va funktsional ko'rsatkichlari bo'yicha

maxsus jismoniy tayyorgarlik darajasi etarlicha yuqori emas, deb hisoblaydilar; 52%i ushbu darajani koordinatsion qobilyatini rivojlantirish hisobiga oshirish mumkin, deb hisoblaydilar; 44%i musobaqa davrining haftalik mikrosiklida qisqa masofaga yuguruvchi sportchilarning qo'llaniladigan amaliyot kabi portlovchi kuch va ishqalanish kuch yo'nalishli yuklamalarni rejalashtirishni tavsiya qiladilar; mutaxassislarning 64%i esa buning uchun maxsus kuch tayyorgarligiga ega yuklamalardan foydalanish kerakligini ta'kidlaydilar. Qisqa masofaga yuguruvchi yugurish texnikasini butun yil bo'yi o'rganishi va takomillashtirishi kerak. Buning uchun tezlanishli yugurishdan, to'la kuch sarflamay masofaning ma'lum qismlarini yugurib o'tishdan, shuningdek, qisqa masofa yuguruvchi mashg'ulotida muxim o'rin tutishi kerak bo'lgan maxsus tayyorlov mashqlaridan foydalanish kerak. Biomexanik parametrlarni aniqlash va tahlil qilish: qisqa masofaga yugurish texnikasining asosiy biomexanik parametrlarini aniqlash (oyoq harakati, qadam uzunligi, qadam chastotasi, tana og'irligi markazi harakati, kuchlanish burchaklari va o'zaro bog'liqliklar) yugurish jarayonida yuqori va past ko'rsatkichlarga sabab bo'luvchi texnik elementlari aniqlandi va tahlil qilindi.

REFERENCES

1. Балтаева И. Т. и др. USE OF VIRTUAL LABORATORIES TO CONDUCT FOOTBALL TRAINING //MODERN SCIENCE AND RESEARCH. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 709-718.
2. Jumayev U. X., Kazoqov R. T., Abdusalomov I. K. QUANTITATIVE EVALUATION OF QUALITY INDICATORS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 229-240.
3. Qutlimurotov I. X. et al. THE PROCESS OF ORGANIZING EDUCATIONAL ACTIVITIES OF STUDENTS AND MASTERING PERSONAL PROFESSIONAL KNOWLEDGE //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 869-879.
4. Солиев И. Р. и др. МОРФО-ФУНКЦИОНАЛ ВА АНТРОПОГЕНЕТИК ТАДҚИҚОТ НАТИЖАЛАРГА КЎРА ФУТБОЛЧИЛАРНИНГ ИШЧАНЛИК НАТИЖАЛАРИНИ БАШОРАТ ҚИЛИШ //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 6.
5. Тажибаев С. С. и др. ЖАХОН ЧЕМПИОНАТИ 2022 ЙИЛГИ ФУТБОЛЧИЛАР АНТРОПОМЕТРИК ЎЛЧАМЛАРИ ВА ТЕЗЛИК СИФАТИ ОРАСИДАГИ КОРРЕЛЯЦИЯНИ ЎРГАНИШ //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 6.
6. Тажибаев С. С. и др. 13-14 ЁШЛИ ФУТБОЛЧИЛАРНИНГ ТЕХНИК-ТАКТИК ҲАРАКАТЛАРИНИ ТАРБИЯЛАШ САМАРАДОРЛИГИ //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 6.
7. Boltayeva I. T. et al. PERIODS OF PRODUCTION EDUCATION. THE PERIOD OF INITIATION, PREPARATION, ACQUISITION AND COMPLETION OF THE PROFESSION //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 561-569.
8. Ganieva M. et al. THE UNITY OF TECHNIQUE, TACTICS AND STRATEGY IN TABLE TENNIS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 5. – С. 1175-1183.
9. Usmonova S. H., Akmurodov M., Kazokov R. THE INFLUENCE OF TEMPERAMENT ON THE CHOICE OF SPORTS ACTIVITIES //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 5. – С. 63-70.

10. Umaraliyeva F. T., Kazoqov R. T. THE ROLE OF SPORTSWOMEN IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIETY AND IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SPORTS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 5. – С. 1124-1131.
11. Mustafayeva N. A., Kazoqov R. T. USING THE MAIN CHARACTERISTICS AND POSSIBILITIES OF THE ELECTRONIC SCHEDULE IN SOLVING ISSUES RELATED TO PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORTS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 5. – С. 1115-1123.
12. Kazoqov R. T., Axatov L. K. SPORT TOMOSHASINING ESTETIKASI. – 2024.
13. Jumayev U. X. et al. " PEDAGOGICAL EDUCATION INNOVATION CLUSTER" MEANS COMMON GOALS AND SPECIFIC INTERESTS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 552-560.
14. Umarov D. X. et al. NATIONAL MOVEMENT FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS'PHYSICAL PREPARATION USING GAMES //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 732-741.
15. Umarov D. X. et al. THE EFFECTIVENESS OF USING A SET OF SPECIAL EXERCISES IN ANNUAL PREPARATION TRAINING OF SHORT-DISTANCE RUNNERS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 742-753.
16. Jumayev U. X. et al. " PEDAGOGICAL EDUCATION INNOVATION CLUSTER" MEANS COMMON GOALS AND SPECIFIC INTERESTS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 552-560.
17. Turopovich K. R., Rixsibayevna D. S. ENHANCING ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNING THROUGH PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES. – 2024.
18. Kazakov R. T. et al. MULTIMEDIA SYSTEMS AND DISTANCE LEARNING TECHNIQUES IN SPORTS SOX //Modern Science and Research. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 9. – С. 99-105.
19. Казоқов Р. Т. и др. МАМЛАКАТИМИЗ ЯНАДА ЮКСАЛИШИДА БОЛАЛАР СПОРТИНИНГ ЎРНИ //Академические исследования в современной науке. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 9. – С. 5-11.
20. Казоқов Р. Т. и др. ПЕДАГОГИКА ОЛИЙ ТАЪЛИМДА КЕЙС-СТАДИ ТАЪЛИМ ТЕХНОЛОГИЯСИ АСОСИДА ПЕДАГОГИК МАҲОРАТИНИ ШАКЛЛАНТИРИШ ЮЗАСИДАН ТАЖРИБА-СИНОВ ИШЛАРИНИНГ НАТИЖАЛАРИ //Академические исследования в современной науке. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 6. – С. 111-115.
21. Казоқов Р. Т. Кейс стади технологияларидан фойдаланиб талабаларнинг масофавий таълим технологиялари асосида педагогик маҳоратини шакллантириш //Замонавий футболни ривожлантириш тенденциялари: муаммо ва ечимлари. – Т. 11. – №. 1.
22. Jumayev U. X. et al. " PEDAGOGICAL EDUCATION INNOVATION CLUSTER" MEANS COMMON GOALS AND SPECIFIC INTERESTS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 552-560.
23. Musaeva U., Mirzaeva U. Дерматоглифические показатели как критерии для прогнозирования уровня развития двигательных качеств у спортсменов с учетом этнических особенностей //Sport ilm-fanining dolzarb muammolari. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 3. – С. 110-112.

24. Achilov O. H. TO INCREASE THE INTEREST OF ELEMENTARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN SPORTS AND TO MAKE THEM REGULARLY ENGAGE IN SPORTS //Educational Research in Universal Sciences. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 1. – С. 218-220.
25. SEIDALIEVA L. D., MUSAEVA U. A., KHAIDAROV T. S. Comparative Assessment of Physical Development and Component Composition of the Body Weight of Sportswoman Participated in Gymnastics //Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies. – 2023. – Т. 17. – С. 87-90.
26. Musaev M. T., Musaeva U. A. JISMONIY FAOLLIK VA UNING INSON SALOMATLIGINI MUSTAHKAMLASHDAGI AHAMIYAT //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2023. – №. 1. – С. 267-273.
27. Safarova D. D., Musaeva U. A., Khushvakova N. Y. ПОКАЗАТЕЛИ ПАЛЬЦЕВОЙ И ЛАДОННОЙ ДЕРМАТОГЛИФИКИ В АСПЕКТЕ ПОЛОВОЙ ИДЕНТИФИКАЦИИ //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 1. – С. 326-332.
28. Umarov D. X. et al. THE EFFECTIVENESS OF USING A SET OF SPECIAL EXERCISES IN ANNUAL PREPARATION TRAINING OF SHORT-DISTANCE RUNNERS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 742-753.
29. Jumayev U. X. et al. " PEDAGOGICAL EDUCATION INNOVATION CLUSTER" MEANS COMMON GOALS AND SPECIFIC INTERESTS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 552-560.
30. Boltayeva I. T., Tashnazarov D. Y., Kazaqov R. T. TECHNICAL-TACTICS OF 13-14-YEAR-OLD FOOTBALL PLAYERS EFFICIENCY OF EDUCATIONAL ACTIONS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 6. – С. 91-98.
31. Kazoqov R. et al. MARKETING TIZIMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH ORQALI SPORT TASHKILOTLARI FAOLIYATI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH YOLLARI //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 10. – С. 572-578.
32. Aripov Y. Y. et al. PROFESSIONAL SPORTNI BOSHQARISH MODELLARI //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 10. – С. 597-587.
33. Jumayev U. X. et al. SPORT SOHASIDA MARKETING FAOLIYATINI RIVOJLANTIRSH //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 10. – С. 588-597.
34. Умаров Д. Х. и др. USE OF NATIONAL-SPIRITUAL VALUES IN EDUCATIONAL ACTIVITIES OF PRE-SCHOOL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 10. – С. 455-462.
35. Рахматова Д. Н. и др. EXPERIMENTAL WORK ON THE ORGANIZATION OF SPIRITUAL AND EDUCATIONAL WORK AND ITS RESULTS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 10. – С. 447-454.
36. Djalilova S., Tursunboyeva L., Kazakhov R. ENGAGING ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNING THROUGH SPORTS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 10. – С. 386-395.
37. Tursunboyeva L., Djalilova S., Kazoqov R. ABOUT TEACHING SPEAKING //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 10. – С. 376-385.

38. Jumayev U. X. et al. " PEDAGOGICAL EDUCATION INNOVATION CLUSTER" MEANS COMMON GOALS AND SPECIFIC INTERESTS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 552-560.
39. Boltayeva I. T., Tashnazarov D. Y., Kazaqov R. T. TECHNICAL-TACTICS OF 13-14-YEAR-OLD FOOTBALL PLAYERS EFFICIENCY OF EDUCATIONAL ACTIONS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 6. – С. 91-98.
40. Boltayeva I. T. et al. ANATOMY OF THE EXACT AND NATURAL SCIENCES TEST TASK //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 6. – С. 99-105.
41. Казоқов Р. Т. и др. ТАЪЛИМ МУАССАСАЛАРИДА ТАРБИЯВИЙ ТАДБИРЛАРДА МИЛЛИЙ-МАЪНАВИЙ ҚАДРИЯТЛАРДАН ФОЙДАЛАНИШ. – 2024.
42. Djurayeva X. X., Xodjiyev R. M., Kazaqov R. T. DIFFICULTIES IN TEACHING RUSSIAN AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 316-326.
43. Beknazarov S. H. Q., Kazaqov R. T. IDEOLOGICAL THREATS AND IMPORTANT PROBLEMS OF IDEOLOGICAL EDUCATION, NATIONAL HISTORICAL THINKING //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 1016-1029.
44. Boltayeva I. T. et al. ANATOMY OF THE EXACT AND NATURAL SCIENCES TEST TASK //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 6. – С. 99-105.
45. Бойқобилов А. П. и др. ТУРЛИ МАЛАКАЛИ СПОРТЧИЛАР ТОМОНИДАН ЯДРО УЛОҚТИРИШНИНГ НАЗАРИЙ ТАҲЛИЛЛАРИ //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 10. – С. 30-40.
46. Авезова Г. С., Казоқов Р. Т. ҚИСҚА МАСОФАГА ЮГУРУВЧИЛАРНИ МАШҒУЛОТ ЖАРАЁНИДА ҚЎЛЛАНИЛГАН ТИКЛОВЧИ ВОСИТАЛАРНИ ЖИСМОНИЙ ТАЙЁРГАРЛИГИГА ТАЪСИРИ //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 10. – С. 205-214.
47. Шопулатов А. Н., Казоқов Р. Т., Хайдарова Г. М. ҚИСҚА МАСОФАГА ЮГУРУВЧИЛАРНИ ЖИСМОНИЙ ТАЙЁРГАРЛИГИНИ БАҲОЛАШ //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 10. – С. 197-204.
48. Бойқобилов А. П. и др. ТУРЛИ МАЛАКАЛИ СПОРТЧИЛАР ТОМОНИДАН ЯДРО УЛОҚТИРИШНИНГ НАЗАРИЙ ТАҲЛИЛЛАРИ //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 10. – С. 30-40.
49. Yugay L. P. et al. RECOVERY OF THE BODY OF SHORT-DISTANCE RUNNING ATHLETES DURING SPORTS TRAINING //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 365-371.
50. Akbarov A. et al. ANTHROPOMETRIC-PHYSIOLOGICAL INDICATORS OF MIDDLE-DISTANCE RUNNERS AND RECOVERY OF THEIR BODY DURING TRAINING //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 358-364.
51. Kim D. et al. PEDAGOGICAL ANALYSIS OF THE PARTICIPATION OF STUDENT ATHLETES IN THE SWEDISH TEAM AND THE SWEDISH TEAM IN THE UZBEKISTAN CHAMPIONSHIP IN HEIGHT ATHLETICS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 346-353.

52. Nurullayeva D. S. et al. ETHICAL PROBLEMS AND THEM IN THE FIELD OF NATURE SOLUTIONS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 480-486.
53. Kazaqov R. T., Djo'rabayev A. M. MEANS OF RECOVERY OF WORKING CAPACITY OF SHORT-DISTANCE RUNNERS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 902-911.
54. Kazoqov R. T., Djo'rabayev A. M. DEVELOPMENT OF CYBER SPORTS IN UZBEKISTAN //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 893-901.
55. Yaqubov F. M. et al. METHODOLOGY OF SELECTION OF 10-12-YEAR-OLD PLAYERS AND ORGANIZATION OF TRAINING //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 1271-1279.
56. Казоқов Р. Т. ҚИСҚА МАСОФАГА ЮГУРУВЧИЛАРНИНГ ЖИСМОНИЙ ВА МАХСУС ЖИСМОНИЙ ТАЙЁРГАРЛИК КЎРСАТКИЧЛАРИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ //Fan-Sportga. – 2022. – №. 7. – С. 53-55.
57. Гонашвили А. С. и др. Активный досуг узбекской молодежи в аспекте социологического анализа //Теория и практика физической культуры. – 2020. – №. 3. – С. 8-8.
58. Baltayeva I. T. et al. USE OF VIRTUAL LABORATORIES TO CONDUCT FOOTBALL TRAINING //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 709-718.
59. Baltayeva I. T. et al. CREATING AN INFORMATION-EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT USING MODERN INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 700-708.
60. Melziddinov R. A., Akramov B. N., Kazoqov R. T. THE RELATIONSHIP OF THE EFFICIENCY OF TECHNICAL-TACTICAL ACTIONS OF FOOTBALL PLAYERS WITH THE LEVEL OF PHYSICAL PREPARATION //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 1153-165.
61. Umarov D. X. et al. NATIONAL MOVEMENT FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS'PHYSICAL PREPARATION USING GAMES //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 732-741.
62. Umarov D. X. et al. THE EFFECTIVENESS OF USING A SET OF SPECIAL EXERCISES IN ANNUAL PREPARATION TRAINING OF SHORT-DISTANCE RUNNERS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 742-753.
63. Шопулатов А. Н. Бўлажак мураббийларда жисмоний тарбия ва спорт асосида маънавий кадрятларни ривожлантириш йўллари //Фан-Спортга. – 2019. – №. 1. – С. 67-72.
64. Boltayeva I. T., Tashnazarov D. Y., Kazaqov R. T. TECHNICAL-TACTICS OF 13-14-YEAR-OLD FOOTBALL PLAYERS EFFICIENCY OF EDUCATIONAL ACTIONS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 6. – С. 91-98.
65. Boltayeva I. T. et al. ANATOMY OF THE EXACT AND NATURAL SCIENCES TEST TASK //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 6. – С. 99-105.
66. Казоқов Р. Т. и др. ТАЪЛИМ МУАССАСАЛАРИДА ТАРБИЯВИЙ ТАДБИРЛАРДА МИЛЛИЙ-МАЪНАВИЙ ҚАДРИЯТЛАРДАН ФОЙДАЛАНИШ. – 2024.

67. Умаров Д. Х. и др. USE OF NATIONAL-SPIRITUAL VALUES IN EDUCATIONAL ACTIVITIES OF PRE-SCHOOL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 10. – С. 455-462.
68. Kazoqov R. T. et al. USE OF NATIONAL-SPIRITUAL VALUES IN EDUCATIONAL ACTIVITIES IN EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 5. – С. 911-918.
69. Керимов Ф. А. и др. ORGANIZATION OF SPIRITUAL AND EDUCATIONAL WORK IN PRE-SCHOOL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS AND FAMILY COOPERATION //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 10. – С. 463-470.
70. Рахматова Д. Н. и др. EXPERIMENTAL WORK ON THE ORGANIZATION OF SPIRITUAL AND EDUCATIONAL WORK AND ITS RESULTS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 10. – С. 447-454.